

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B111
Date: 14 Jul 2005
Take Off 08:36:03
Landing: 13:16:32
Flight Time 4h40m29s

Campaign: AMPEP
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: Norfolk to Scotland east coast

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	David Fowler	CEH
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	CCM2/Filters	Paul James	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
8	AMS	Paul Williams	Manchester University
9	AMS training	Gerrard Capes	Manchester University
10	Core chem / TDLAS	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
11	Core Chem training	Maureen Smith	FAAM
12	PAN/WAS	Maria Nielsdottir	UEA
13	Bags 1	Alan McDonald	CEH
14	Bags 2	Mark Theobald	CEH
15	Ptr-MS	Anne Hulse	UEA
16	Ptr-MS training	Jennifer Murphy	UEA
17	NOxy	Dave Stewart	UEA
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B111 Track 14-JUL-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b111
 Date: 14 Jul 05
 Project: AMPEP
 Location: east coast

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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081308		INU to nav	0.14 kft	127	gps 52'04.36N 000'37.48W
082704		start & power c/o	0.14 kft	127	
082827		taxy	0.14 kft	129	
083603		T/O Cranfield	3.9 kft	359	08:36:03
084009		asps open	5.0 kft	058	
084117		video recording star	5.0 kft	055	FFC & DFC
084155		ams logging rosemoun	6.3 kft	057	
084441	090100	Run 1	10.0 kft	063	fl100 calcs stop at WP 40
085110		nev cal	10.0 kft	065	fl100
090307	090641	Profile 1	9.5 - 6.0 kft	297	10000-6000ft
090641	090752	Run 2	6.0 - 5.9 kft	300	run 2 fl60
090752	090934	Profile 2	5.9 - 4.0 kft	301	fl60-40
090934	091027	Run 3	4.0 kft	297	fl40
091028	091237	Profile 3	4.0 - 2.0 kft	288	
091238	091332	Run 4	2.0 kft	295	run 4 2000'
091333	091453	Profile 4	2.0 - 0.80 kft	310	
091453	091548	Run 5	0.80 - 0.81 kft	337	run 5 1000'
091548	091727	Profile 5	0.81 - -.09 kft	335	
091727	091833	Run 6	-.09 - -.01 kft	332	run 6 100'
091943	092140	Run 7	0.81 - 0.79 kft	332	run 7 1000' ams crash
092926	104250	Run 8	0.79 - 0.94 kft	331	1000'
093300		waypoint 80	0.79 kft	317	
094930		waypoint 79	0.82 kft	335	
100534		waypoint 77	0.88 kft	335	718nm N of Paris
101300		waypoint 76	0.89 kft	341	
103209		waypoint 75	0.94 kft	009	
104456	104543	Run 9	0.09 - 0.12 kft	176	run 9 100ft
104544	104621	Profile 6	0.12 - 0.50 kft	178	
104622	104711	Run 10	0.50 - 0.53 kft	180	run 10 500ft
104711	104754	Profile 7	0.53 - 0.96 kft	181	
104754	104846	Run 11	0.96 - 0.95 kft	179	run 11 1000ft
104846	104946	profile 8	0.95 - 1.9 kft		
104946	105051	Run 12	1.9 kft	178	run 12 2000ft
105051	105252	Profile 9	1.9 - 4.0 kft	178	
105252	105354	Run 13	4.0 kft	178	run 13 fl40
105355	105548	Profile 10	4.0 - 6.0 kft	178	
105618	105710	Run 14	6.0 kft	206	run 14 fl60
105710	110045	Profile 11	6.0 - 10.0 kft	211	
110045	110154	Run 15	10.0 kft	196	run 15 fl100
110238		descent to 1000'	10.0 kft	193	
111358	123757	Run 16	0.92 - 0.80 kft	180	run 16 1000ft
111550		waypoint 76	0.94 kft	172	
114032		waypoint 79	0.87 kft	170	
114213		QNH 1019	0.88 kft	141	
115729		waypoint 80	0.88 kft	151	
121828		waypoint 87	0.83 kft	128	
121841		QNH 1021	0.82 kft	123	
122627		TW status light ON	0.80 kft	148	
123707		TW status 4094	0.80 kft	201	
123719		TW 'off'	0.80 kft	201	
123746		TW 'on'	0.80 kft	201	
123850	124319	Profile 12	0.82 - 5.0 kft	308	slow climb in plume
124302		TW restarted ok	4.7 kft	323	
124545		fl100 calibrations	10.0 kft	311	
130933		asps closed	2.4 kft	234	
131632		Land	0.22 kft	311	13:16:32
131928		power c/o	0.22 kft	311	

B111 Track 14-JUL-05

Sortie Brief: AMPEP

Flight Number : B111

Mission Scientist: David Fowler, CEH

Date 14-July-2005

Outline schedule:

06:00 – Power to aircraft – warm-up
08:00 – Briefing
09:15 – Clear aircraft and security check
09:30 – Doors close
10:00 – Take off Cranfield
14:00 – Land Teesside for refueling;
15:30 – Take off Teesside
17:05 – Land Cranfield
17:35 - Debrief
19:05 – Power down

Location: Northbound followed by Southbound transect of the East Coast of England and Scotland

Sortie Aims: To measure the UK pollutant budget of a range of gases and aerosols leaving the UK in gentle Westerly airflow over northern Britain. The objective, in addition to measuring the export fluxes of pollutants is to derive the chemical processing (gas/aerosol partitioning & oxidation state) of the air mass in Westerly airflow over the UK. The frontal activity to the North and West limits the area of the UK over which we can work, and the lack of airflow over southern England restricts the work to areas north of Norfolk according to current forecasts.

Sortie Summary: The budget measurements will be obtained by flying off the East coast along a Northbound transect beginning off the coast of Norfolk, and ending at Wick, then after refueling (in Inverness) to return along the same path returning to Cranfield. Vertical profiles (50 – 6000 ft) once upwind at the North end of the transect and downwind of the source region off the Lincolnshire coast on the Southbound leg will provide the vertical structure in concentration and meteorology. These should clearly extend into the free troposphere (Mission Scientist to verify from profiles of humidity, temperature and CO. These measurements will establish the upwind concentration, the concentration differential at the top of the boundary layer and the concentration in the outflow from the source region. Flight ceiling will be 10000ft. Cabin pressure will be maintained at 1200ft, to minimize expansion of the Tedlar bags.

Sortie Detail with approx timing

- a) Take off Cranfield 10:00 and climb to 10000 ft for transit east to operating area. Destination waypoint 40 near East Anglia; background filter run & NO_x calibration.
- b) T+20 Profile down to define the boundary layer structure off the coast with 1 min sampling at each height (6000, 4000, 2000, 1000, 500, 100)

- c) T+35 Return to 1000 ft for sampling.
Start of filter run No 1. Start of Bag sampling (1 bag every min) continue all the way up the east coast.
- d) T+160 background profile at point 74 (dip to 50ft, ascent at 1000 ft min⁻¹, level out at 100, 500, 2000, 4000, 6000 for 1 min each, approx. 15 min profile duration)
- e) T+240 land Teesside
- f) T+330 T/O Teesside
- g) T+340 before leaving coast near WP87; downwind profile heading north (dip to 50ft, ascent at 1000 ft min⁻¹, level out at 100, 500, 2000, 4000, 6000 for 1 min each, approx. 15 min profile duration); followed by NO_x calibration
- h) T+ 400 Land Cranfield

Crew List:

1. Pilot 1 - Alan Roberts
2. Pilot 2 – Alan Foster
3. CCM – Sue Angold
4. CCM 2 Steve Devereau
5. Cloud Physics – Martyn Pickering
6. CVI Paul James
7. Flight Manager – Jim Crawford
8. Mission Scientist – David Fowler
9. Core Chemistry/TDLAS/PAN – Ruth Purvis
10. Core Chemistry Training Maureen Smith
11. Filters – Steve Devereau
12. WAS – Maria Nielsdottir
13. Bag Sampling 1 – Alan McDonald
14. Bag Sampling 2 – Mark Theobald
15. AMS – Paul Williams
16. PTRMS – Anne Hulse
17. PTRMS–Training Jennifer Murphy
18. NO_x – Dave Stewart

MAPS:

Cranfield T/O 8:45
40
87
80
79
78
77
76
75
74
75
76
Refuel at Teesside
77
78
79
80
87
40
Cranfield land.

Tuesday 12 July 2005 00UTC ©ECMWF Forecast t+060 VT: Thursday 14 July 2005 12UTC
Surface: 2 metre temperature / 30 Metres Wind

Instrumentation strategies & issues:

Filter sampling: Filters will be taken throughout the flight. Filter pack 1 will contain a Teflon filter for trace metal analysis. Filter pack 2 will contain a Teflon prefilter (for major ion analysis), a nylon filter (for HNO_3 & HCl) and an acidified paper filter (for NH_3). Filters will be changed approximately every 30 minutes or when flight conditions change (as advised by the Mission Scientist). Filters are preloaded into cartridges, which need to be handled with gloves and stored in sealed bags immediately. Filter sampling will be suspended during vertical profiles and resumed when FL10 is re-attained. During breaks, filter packs will be isolated by switching off the pump (to minimise evaporation of volatile aerosol components). During initial transfer to the operating area, a set of filters should be loaded into the filter packs, without sampling, to provide a blank value. Three 30-min runs of filters on each leg (S→N and N→S)

AMS: The AMS will be operated continuously during the flight. Monitored masses will include m/z 16, 18, 28, 30, 43, 44, 46, 57 and 64. The inlet remains closed until airborne to minimize contamination during taxi take-off.

Core Chemistry: CO , SO_2 , NO and NO_2 will be measured continuously during the flight. CO will be calibrated every 30 minutes at FL10.

Tedlar bags: Tedlar bags will be filled at a flow rate of 6 lpm, filling a bag over a duration of 30 s. Bags will be filled every 3 minutes upwind and every minute downwind of the source region and during each leveling out for a profile step. Bags should be filled to about 90% of their capacity to maximise sample volume. The cabin pressure will be tightly controlled. Bags from first part of flight can be stored in cargo hold for second part.

Aerosol & cloud physics: CN and PCASP are operated continuously.

Core meteorology & state: Are recorded as standard. Video recording of front facing and downfacing cameras.

PTRMS: Operation as normal.

NOxy: Operation as normal; calibration during transits at FL100

WAS: Sampling density and location to be decided.

TDL for CH₄ and CO₂: Operated by FAAM.

Quick-look data: pressure height, lat, long, temp, RH, CN, SO₂, NO, NO₂, O₃, CO

Take off from Cranfield at 08:37 climbing to 10,000ft and heading East to the Norfolk coast, during which NO_x calibration and background filter samples were taken during Run 1 beginning 08:45. Run 2 beginning 09:05, with bag filling at 6000ft provided background air samples, close to the Norfolk coast. Run 3 at 4000ft close to Cromer, Run 4 at 2000ft, Run 5 at 1000ft, Run 6 at 100ft. Climb to 1000ft for sampling the transect north as Run 7, at 09:19. The run was halted at 09:21 to climb to 5000ft and correct a problem with the AMS, off the Lincolnshire coast. The sampling at 1000ft restarted at 09:26 with gentle westerly airflow. Plumes of SO₂ and NO₂ to 20ppb and 40 ppb respectively shortly before reaching the Teesside area. A series of distinct plumes of gaseous and particulate pollutants with a small background concentrations between each.

Visibility declining close to the Farne Isles as the 1000ft sampling continued north, towards WP76. Plumes of SO₂ and NO₂ in the Firth of Forth downwind of the Lothians and Central Scotland. End of Run, north of Peterhead.

Profile sampling to define the vertical structure, 100ft, 1000ft, 2000ft, 4000ft, 6000ft at 10:56. Return to 1000ft for sampling on the southbound route along the coastline, as Run 16. The plumes of SO₂ and NO₂, on the return sampling were similar to those measured on the northbound route, and were particularly clear off Teesside, with SO₂ and NO₂ concentrations of 16ppb and 27 ppb respectively in the plumes. The plumes off the Yorkshire coast close to WP 80 were distinct and with high SO₂ relative to the NO₂ concentrations seem likely to be from the coal burning power stations in the Ferrybridge to Eggborough area. Sampling continued around the Lincolnshire and Norfolk coasts and south to Suffolk stopping close to the Sizewell Nuclear power station.

Return to Cranfield at 10000ft with NO_x calibration during the transit, landing at Cranfield at approx 13:15.

David Fowler, CEH

18 pm 10 min
WAS

Mission Scientist's Log

D. Fowler

Flight No **B.111**.....

Date **14 July 05**.....

Page **1** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0730					Flight briefing 0730 noted per weather
					North of WP 75. plan to profile at WP 75
					and return along same route. Plan for
					3 sites N bound and 3 sites S bound.
	GMT ↓				
0845					Prep & recording
0930					Prep for take off Cranfield
0937					take off clouds to 10% heading
0945	1	10k			heading E to Norfolk coast
1005	2	6k			Norfolk coast Bay filling
1007	P2				profiling to 4k ~ CRAMER
1010	3	4k			Bay filling, out 4k ~ "
1011	P3				profiling to 2 1/2 ^{clear} MORGAN BLAKENEY
1012	4	2k			
09:13	P4				profiling to 1 1/2
09:15	5	1k			Bag & bottle filling
09:16	6	100ft			Profile to 100ft
					Climb to 1000 f
19	7	1k			
09:21					End of Run AMS Cranfield (Humber)
		5k			Climb to 5k & start AMS
09:26					Return to 1000
09:29	8	1k			Approx Fleckby gl. field
09:38	8	1k			240° 8kt & gusts 10-15

Mission Scientist's Log

Drew...

Flight No **B. 111**

Date **14-07-05**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
09:42	8	1000	330		poor visibility w/ hazy
09:48	8	1000			plumes of SO ₂ to 2000m 40ppb NO _x
09:50	8	1000	320		traceable
09:52	8	1000	310		Newcastle hazy
09:56	8	1000	310		Aberdeen 7000 NO _x 110ppb SO ₂
09:59	8	1000	310		downwind Newcastle 10ppb NO _x 0.50
					Disin. plumes from 2 coast towns
					low background - (are we in it?)
10:02	8	1000	300		1.2 ppb SO ₂ 8 ppb NO _x ^{FAO 15} / ^{FAO 15} Aberdeen
10:09	8	1000	300		1.2 NO ₂ 8 ppb NO _x
10:11	8	1000	200		Visibility declining CR↓ Beirut
10:13	8	1000	300		WP76
10:18	8	1000	300		Spurb SO ₂ 10 ppb NO _x downwind CEli
10:22	8	1000	300		Aberdeen, heading to Aberdeen downwind
10:26	8	1000	300		Aberdeen - wind 250 27kt
10:40	8	1000	350		SO ₂ N Aberdeen 0.20 NO _x 8 ppb NO _x
10:42	8a	1000			End of Run 8 descend to 1000ft
10:45	9	100	180		low level run, S
10:46	P6				profile to 500
10:46:22	10	500	180		500ft run
10:47	P7				profile to 1000ft
10:48	11	1000	180		1000ft run (-0.1 ppb NO _x)
10:49	P8				profile to 2000ft
10:50	12	2000	180		2000ft run (-0.1 ppb NO _x)
10:51	P9				profile to 4000ft

Mission Scientist's Log

D. Fournier

Flight No **B**.....111.....

Date 14-07-2009

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:52	P3	4000	180		
10:53	P10				1000 to 5000 ft
10:56	P14	6000	180		0.2 ppm at least 40 ppb ^{ppb} → 50
10:57	P11				ppb 16 to 18 K ft
11:00	P15	1000	180		run at flight level 1000
11:02					End of run
11:06	P12				descend to 1000 ft ft. terrain (sea)
11:13	P16	1000	170		Ferns of Ferns - Gas plume
11:22	P16	1000	"		Ferns Islands, Kofu Island (Shonan ^{ppb} 120)
11:28	P16	1000	214		1 ppb NO ₂ , 10 ppb O ₃
11:34	P16	1000	215		7 ppb NO ₂ , 1 ppb NO, 13 ppb O ₃
11:36	P16	1000			
11:40	P16	1000	134		WP 70, 3 NO ₂ , 13 ppb O ₃
11:43	P16	1000			General 27 ppb NO ₂ , 16 ppb O ₃ ^{max CO} 1 ppm
					A excellent transition of plumes
11:48	P16	1000	144		1 ppb NO ₂ , 12 ppb O ₃ , New York coast
11:50	P16	1000	143		Flamethrower plume
11:56	P16	1000	144		US Navy plume S.F. Hd WPSO ^{0.3 ppm}
11:57	P16	1000	150		18 ppb NO ₂ Wind 216° 11 kt
12:02	P16	1000	154		2.3 ppb NO ₂ , 20 ppb SO ₂ , 20 ppb CO
12:10	P16	1000	157		Line plume from S. 2 ppb NO ₂ , 20 ppb O ₃
12:16	P16	1000	160		Navy fire, 1.3 ppb NO ₂ , 18 ppb O ₃
12:22	P16	"	160		Crimes, 2 ppb NO ₂
12:26	P16	1000	147		S. Pacific 6 ppb NO ₂

FLIGHT NUMBER: B111	DATE: 14.7.05	OPERATOR: Doug Anderson	Page 2
PROJECT: AMPEP			

CORE CHEMISTRY CALIBRATION AND FLOW LOG

PREVIOUS CO CAL		Date and Flight Level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)
08:56:55	100	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		69.97	97.57	6827	50.0	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample		
33.80	0.65	0.65			0.344		
693431	1000ft	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		71.92	97.17	6989	50	7.14	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample		
33.82							
10:08:58	1000ft	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		72.96	95.85	6993.10	50.00	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample		
33.74	9.0	9.0			0.14		
10:39:00	1000ft	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		73.88	94.85	7008.00	50.00	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample		
33.91	8.0	9.0			0.21		
11:25:10	1000ft	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		74.93	93.49	7005.51	50.00	7.14	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample		
33.69	11.0	11.0			0.39		
≈ 1140 CO = 1538 ppb! sharp plume		CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample
12:19:40	1000ft	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		75.43	91.84	6926.95	50.0	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample		
33.61	18.0	18.0			0.66		

CORE CHEMISTRY CALIBRATION AND FLOW LOG

Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
12:51:20	FL100	75.12	91.44	6869.05	50.00	7.14	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample
		33.85	20	23			0.24
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
Flows (LPM unless stated)							
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
Flows (LPM unless stated)							
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
Flows (LPM unless stated)							
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B111

Date: 09/08/05

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	
08:44:41											Start Run 1 @ FL100
08:45:00	20	0.07	0								Slight indication of PCASP noise
08:47:00	10	0.07									Slight indication of PCASP noise
08:49:00	15	0.09									Slight indication of PCASP noise
08:51:00	15	0.09									Slight indication of PCASP noise
08:53:00	80	0.10									
08:55:00	40	0.09									
08:57:00	35	0.09									
08:59:00	15	0.10									
09:00:58											End of Run 1
09:02:38	11	0.10									Start Profile 1 from FL100
09:03:29	70	0.09									FL090
09:04:21	300	0.09									FL080
09:05:25	400	0.09									FL070
09:06:37	550	0.10									End of P1 & Start Run 2 @ FL060
09:07:38											End Run 2 Start P2 from FL060
09:08:35	630	0.09									FL050
09:09:34	500	0.09									End of P2 Start Run 3 @ 4000'
09:10:28											End of Run 3 Start P3 from 4000'
09:11:29	700	0.09									3000'
09:12:38	660	0.09									End of P3 Start Run 4 @ 2000'
09:13:29											End of Run 4 Start P4 from 2000'
09:14:53	1200	0.09									End of P4 Start Run 5 @ 1000'
09:15:49											End of Run 5 Start P5 from 1000'
09:17:30	1000	0.08									End of P5 Start Run 6 @ 100'
09:18:30											End of Run 6
09:19:35											Start Run 7 @ 1000'
09:20:00	320	0.08									
09:21:38											End of Run 7
09:29:25											Start Run 8 @ 1000'
09:30:00	210	0.09									
09:32:00	210	0.08									
09:34:00	200	0.08									
09:36:00	380	0.09									

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B111

Date: 09/08/05

Operator: MAP

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G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
09:38:00	410	0.09	0								
09:40:00	480	0.09									
09:42:00	365	0.09									
09:44:00	400	0.09									
09:46:00	380	0.09	overheat		3	800	1	16	2000	1	FFSSP switched off
09:48:00	400	0.09			7	800	1				09:47:30 PCASP peak of 1200
09:50:00	500	0.09									
09:52:00	480	0.09									
09:54:00	400	0.09									
09:56:00	390	0.09									
09:58:00	380	0.09									
10:00:00	400	0.09									
10:02:00	380	0.09									
10:04:00	465	0.09									
10:06:00	410	0.09									
10:08:00	400	0.09									
10:10:00	400	0.09									
10:12:00	335	0.10									FFSSP on
10:14:00	300	0.10									
10:16:00	330	0.10									
10:18:00	250	0.10									
10:20:00	130	0.10									
10:22:00	120	0.10									
10:24:00	25	0.10									
10:26:00	40	0.08									
10:28:00	60	0.08									
10:30:00	55	0.08									
10:32:00	80	0.08									
10:34:00	60	0.08									
10:36:00	140	0.14			10	800	1	150	1000	1	
10:38:00	75	0.08			2	800	1	200	1000	1	
10:40:00	50	0.09			2	800	1	100	1000	1	
10:42:00	60	0.14			3	800	1	110	1000	1	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B111

Date: 09/08/05

Operator: MAP

Page 3 of 5

G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks	
	DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size		Habit
10:42:50			0								End of Run 8	
10:44:55	65	0.09						75	1000	1	Start Run 9 @ 100'	
10:45:43											End of Run 9 Start P6 from 100'	
10:46:22	65	0.09									End of P6 Start Run 10 @ 500'	
10:47:11											End Run 10 Start P7 from 500'	
10:47:52	60	0.09						25			End of P7 Start Run 11 @ 1000'	
10:48:45											End of Run 11 start P8 from 1000'	
10:49:45	50	0.09	1					250	1000	1	End of P8 Start Run 12 @ 2000'	
10:50:54											End of Run 12 Start P9	
10:51:53	120	0.09	2			5	800	1	1000	1600	1	FL030
10:52:54	100	0.15	6			5	800	1	400	1400	1	End of P9 Start Run 13 @ 4000'
10:53:56												End of Run 13 Start P10
10:54:52	65	0.09	10			2	800	1	200	1800	1	FL050
10:55:48	45	0.10				20	700	1	75	600	1	End of P10 Start Run 14 @ 6000'
10:57:10												End of Run 14 Start P11
10:58:07	70	0.11	11			30	800	8	2000	2000	8	FL070
10:59:03	100	0.21	15			55	800	8	9000	1000	8	FL080
10:59:55	50	0.16	17			3	200	0				FL090
11:00:59												End Of P 14 start run 15 @ FL100
11:01:00	35	0.12				11	800	8				
11:02:38												End of Run
11:13:58												Start Run 16 @ 1000'
11:14:00	500	0.10	181									
11:16:00	400	0.10							75	1000	1	
11:18:00	500	0.13	183			1	800	1	35	1000	1	
11:20:00	540	0.10										
11:22:00	440	0.09										
11:24:00	550	0.10										
11:26:00	600	0.10										
11:28:00	400	0.09										
11:30:00	550	0.09				1	800	1	10			
11:32:00	600	0.12	185			1	800	1	260	2800	1	
11:34:00	560	0.09	188			1	800	1	150	1000	1	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B111

Date: 09/08/05

Operator: MAP

Page 4 of 5

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
11:36:00	580	0.10	198		2	800	1	550	800	1	
11:38:00	320	0.09	201					30			
11:40:00	420	0.09									
11:42:00	465	0.09									
11:42:10	1800	0.09									Plume
11:44:00	470	0.09									
11:46:00	450	0.09									
11:48:00	510	0.09	Overheat								FFSSP switched off
11:50:00	430	0.09									
11:52:00	430	0.09									
11:54:00	460	0.09									
11:56:00	350	0.08									
11:58:00	420	0.08									
12:00:00	380	0.09									
12:02:00	490	0.08									
12:04:00	400	0.09									
12:06:00	400	0.09									
12:08:00	435	0.08									
12:10:00	490	0.08									
12:12:00	300	0.08									
12:14:00	200	0.08									
12:16:00	500	0.08									
12:18:00	745	0.08									FFSSP On
12:20:00	860	0.08									
12:22:00	1000	0.08									
12:24:00	1400	0.08									
12:26:00	1350	0.08									
12:28:00	1150	0.08									
12:30:00	980	0.08									
12:32:00	810	0.08									
12:34:00	1000	0.08									
12:36:00	1000	0.07	Overheat								FFSSP switched off
12:37:54	250	0.07									End of Run 16

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B111

Date: 14/07/2005

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt	Y Y	
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS	Y	CONDOR
3) Log on to FLOODS run mrfb:[pms.fast_ffssp]ffssp_output_binary a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA:	Y Y	Complete, no errors. *.txt files deleted after
4) run mrfb:[pms.fast_ffssp]ffssp_extract_tas a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown	Y 0 240000	Completed
5) run mrfb:[pms.fast_ffssp]ffssp_read a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use the most recent calibration file. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]	 Y 0 Y	Note the calibration file used FFSSP_CAL15072005.TXT Completed
6) In PVWAVE a) .run mrfb:[pms.proc]ffssp_sec_read .run mrfb:[pms.proc]lag b) .run mrfb:[pms.proc]write_procffssp_to_m5 c) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format d) exit	 Y Y	Lag of +6 secs corrected for using JW Completed
7) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name	Y	Completed (left as mfd)

<p>e) TAS: Y</p> <p>f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX</p> <p>g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty</p> <p>h) Start time: 0 if unkown</p> <p>i) End time: 240000 if unknown</p> <p>j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5</p> <p>k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown</p> <p>l) Coefficient choice: 2</p> <p>m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	<p>Y</p> <p>0</p> <p>0</p> <p>240000</p> <p>0.2</p> <p>8</p> <p>2</p>	<p>Completed</p>
<p>10) In PVWAVE</p> <p>i) .run MRFB:[PMS.PROC]WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5</p> <p>ii) write_proc2d_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_proc2d.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2d'</p> <p>iii) exit</p>	<p>Y</p>	<p>Completed</p>
<p>11) MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D</p> <p>b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX</p> <p>c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name</p>	<p>Y</p>	<p>Completed (left as mfda)</p>

Flight No. B111

Route

Date 14/7/2005

Take Off 08:30 GMT

Bag Samplers: A McDONALD, M. THEDBAJN

Sheet No. 1

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
264	—	—			TEST BAG
270	08:48:10	08:48:40	52.5N	0.3E	RUN 1 START
236	08:51:00	08:51:30			10000 FT
395	08:54:00	08:54:30			
487	08:57:00	08:57:30			↓ END OF RUN
837	09:03:50	09:04:20	52.7N	1.7E	START OF DESCENT PROFILE
212	09:06:45	09:07:15			6000 ft
536	09:09:40	09:10:10			4000 ft
485	09:10:40	09:11:10			BETWEEN 4000-3000ft
216	09:12:40	09:13:10			2000 ft
217	09:13:37	09:14:07			BETWEEN 2000-1000ft
490	09:15:00	09:15:30			1000 ft
234	09:17:30	09:18:00	53.3N	0.7E	5000ft
269	09:20:00	09:20:30			START OF RUN 7
201	09:21:00	09:21:30			
483	09:26:00	09:27:00			1 min fill, low flow
340	09:29:30	09:30:00			START OF RUN LOW FLOW
528	09:30:30	09:31:00	53.9N	0.1E	
327	09:31:30	09:32:00			
207	09:32:30	09:33:00			WAYPOINT 80
321	09:33:30	09:34:00			
533	09:34:30	09:35:00			
261	09:35:30	09:36:00	54.1N	0.0E	
237	09:36:30	09:37:00			
211	09:37:30	09:38:00			
262	09:38:30	09:39:00			
204	09:39:30	09:40:00			
488	09:40:30	09:41:00			
235	09:41:30	09:42:00			
268	09:42:30	09:43:00			
338	09:43:30	09:44:00	54.5N	0.6W	
529	09:44:30	09:45:00			
335?	09:45:30	09:46:00			
527	09:46:30	09:47:00			
328	09:47:30	09:48:00			
220	09:48:30	09:49:00	54.8N	0.9W	
486?	09:49:30	09:50:05			1 min 05 sec
333	09:50:30	09:51:00			
540	09:51:30	09:52:00			
266	09:52:30	09:53:00			
477	09:53:30	09:54:00	55.0N	1.1W	

09:00:00

FILE 9-34ft

END OF PROFILE RUN

ABOVE 1000ft

Flight No. Route Date Take Off GMTBag Samplers: Sheet No.

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
504	09:54:31	09:55:00			29 sec FILL
322	09:55:30	09:56:00			
530	09:56:30	09:57:00			
323	09:57:30	09:58:00			
219	09:58:30	09:59:00	55.5N	1.2 W	
326	09:59:30	10:00:00			
471	10:00:30	10:01:00			
263	10:01:30	10:02:00			
481	10:02:30	10:03:00			
334	10:03:30	10:04:00			
332	10:04:30	10:05:00	55.7N	1.4 W	WAYPOINT 77
267	10:05:30	10:06:00			
532	10:06:30	10:07:00			
225	10:07:30	10:08:00			
399	10:08:30	10:09:00			
393	10:09:30	10:10:00	55.9N	1.7 W	
510	10:10:30	10:11:00			
391	10:11:30	10:12:00			
476	10:12:30	10:13:00			WAYPOINT 76
503	10:13:30	10:14:00			
210	10:14:30	10:15:00	56.2N	1.8 W	
206	10:15:30	10:16:00			
329	10:16:30	10:17:00			
507	10:17:30	10:18:00			
231	10:18:30	10:19:00			
331	10:19:30	10:20:00			
312	10:20:30	10:21:00	56.6N	1.8 W	
226	10:21:30	10:22:00			
230	10:22:30	10:23:00			
265	10:23:30	10:24:00			
311	10:24:30	10:25:00			
544	10:25:30	10:26:00			
218	10:26:30	10:27:00			
205	10:27:30	10:28:00			
542	10:28:30	10:29:05			35s FILL 35s FILL
408	10:29:30	10:30:00			
223	10:30:30	10:31:00			
215	10:31:30	10:32:00			
208	10:32:30	10:33:08			
233 233	10:33:30	10:34:00			
209	10:34:34	10:35:05			

Flight No. Route

Date Take Off

Bag Samplers:

Sheet No.

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
238	10:35:30	10:36:00			
546	10:36:30	10:37:00			
213	10:37:30	10:38:04	57.7N	1.7W	
482	10:38:30	10:39:00			
484	10:39:30	10:40:00			
502	10:40:32	10:41:02			
458	10:41:31	10:42:02			
382	10:42:40	10:43:10	58.0N	1.7W	END OF RUN
459	10:45:00	10:45:30			100 ft
509	10:46:25	10:46:55			500 ft
397	10:47:15	10:47:45			1000 500-1000 ft
386	10:48:00	10:48:30			1000 ft
329	10:48:50	10:49:20			1000-2000 ft
526	10:49:50	10:50:20			2000 ft
202	10:51:00	10:51:30			2000 - 4000 ft
478	10:53:00	10:53:30			4000 ft
522	10:54:00	10:54:30			4000 - 4700 ft
543	10:55:50	10:56:20			6000 ft
460	10:57:30	10:58:00			6300 - 7100 ft
475	11:00:50	11:01:20			10,000 ft
548	11:14:10	13:0			Run 1b, 1,000 ft
330	15:00	13:0			
390	16:00	13:0	56.1N	1.7W	
396	17:00	13:0			
472	18:00	13:0			
608	19:00	13:0			
387	20:00	13:0			
400	21:00	13:0			
505	22:00	13:0			
473	23:00	13:0			
381	24:00	13:0	55.6	1.4W	
392	25:00	13:0			
384	26:00	13:0			
385	27:00	13:0			
383	28:00	13:0			
409(?)	29:00	13:0			
474	11:30:00	13:0			
388	31:00	13:0			
398	32:00	13:0			no label
282	33:00	13:0			
557	34:00	13:0			

ASCENDING PROFILE

TUBE Spwt

Flight No. Route
 Date Take Off
 Bag Samplers:
 Sheet No.

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
078	11:35:00	35:30			
024	36:00	36:30	53.0	1.0 W	
658	37:00	37:30			
518	38:00	38:30			
545	39:00	39:30			
250	40:00	40:30			
394	41:00	41:30			
501	42:00	42:30			
389	43:00	:30			
407	44:00	:30			
004	45:00	:30			
436	46:00	:30			
285	47:00	:30	54.5	0.5 W	
652	48:00	:30			
390	49:00	:30			
119	50:00	:30			
132	51:00	:30			stiff valve on bag?
073	52:45	:15			
010	53:00	:30			
170	54:00	:30			
145	55:00	:30			
022	56:00	:30			
613	57:00	:30			Waypoint 20
079	58:00	:30			
122	59:00	:30			
651	12:00:00	12:00 :30			
650	01:00	:30			
085	02:00	:30			
080	03:00	:30			
124	04:00	:30	53.7	0.3 E	
060	05:00	:30			
525	06:00	:30			
506	07:00	:30			
450	08:00	:30			
166	09:00	:30			
143	10:00	:30			
378	11:00	:30			
428	12:00	:30			
142	13:00	:30			
164	14:00	:30			
559	15:00	:30			

WAS Sampling Summary

Flight Number: B111
Date: 14/07/2005

Campaign Name: AMPEP
Operator: M. Neilsdottir (UEA)

Bottle Start Fill Time	Bottle End Fill Time	Bottle Number	Comments	Final Pressure (bar)
9:07:42	9:08:29	16	Run 2 at 6000 ft	3.20
09:09:31	9:10:16	17	In profile	3.27
09:10:34	9:11:19	18	Run 3 at 4000 ft	3.27
09:13:36	9:14:21	19	Run 4 at 2000 ft	3.34
09:15:50	9:16:30	20	Run 5 at 1000 ft	3.34
09:18:27	9:19:07	21	Run 6 at 100 ft	3.36
09:21:35	9:22:35	22	Run 7	3.35
09:31:28	9:32:28	23	Run 8 at 1000 ft	3.36
09:44:18	9:45:18	24	Run 8 at 1000 ft	3.36
09:48:26	9:48:56	25	Run 8 at 1000 ft high Sulphur	3.33
09:49:08	9:49:39	26	Teeside	3.33
09:59:36	10:00:06	27	High NOxy, peak on sulphur	3.30
10:00:22	10:00:52	28	High NOxy, peak on sulphur	3.33
10:10:07	10:10:37	29		3.34
10:19:37	10:20:07	30	Downwind from Edinburgh	3.34
10:34:06	10:34:36	31		3.34
10:39:47	10:40:17	32	High organics from AMS	3.33
10:45:53	10:46:33	49	Run 9 (100 ft)	3.36
10:47:17	10:47:57	50	Run 10 (500 ft)	3.35
10:48:54	10:49:34	51	Run 11 (1000 ft)	3.35
10:50:44	10:51:24	52	Part Run 12	3.34
10:56:46	10:57:26	53	Run 14 (6000 ft)	3.34
11:15:43	11:16:23	54	Run 16 high NOxy (zero AMS)- same plume as caught on way up?	3.35
11:17:27	11:18:07	55	Core chemistry indicates pollution	3.34
11:27:58	11:28:38	56		3.36

11:41:03	11:41:43	57	1000 ft	3.35
11:43:51	11:44:31	58	High CO (up to 1 ppm)	3.35
11:44:37	11:45:07	59	High CO (up to 1 ppm)	3.35
12:00:15	12:00:45	60	High NOx (ppb)	3.10
12:03:18	12:03:48	61	High NO2 (14 ppb); High CO (~200)	3.00
12:15:02	12:015:32	62		3.30
12:32:15	12:32:46	63	Plume? (Possibly London plume)	3.30
12:34:57	12:35:27	64	NOxy levels lower but CO rising	3.34

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B111**

Date: 14/07/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
XR5M GPS		Y	FFSSP		Y
Cruciform GPS		Y	PCASP		Y
Satcom C		Y	2D-P		Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-C		Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope	N	N
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1	N	
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2	y	Y
Heimann	N		HVPS	N	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25	Y	N
G. Eastern		Y	CIP100	Y	N
J. Williams		Y			
Nevzorov		Y			
TWC		Y			
FWVS	Y	N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	Y	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC		Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI		Y
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	Y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	y
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	y
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
SO	y	y	Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	Y
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	Y
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	y
PAN	Y	y	PTRMS	Y	y
PERCA	N	N	Bag Sampling	Y	y
WAS	Y	y			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B111

Date: 14/07/05

Instruments

1. Video – inboard recorder screen in standby
2. TW status light came on late in flight – recycled power – returned to normal working
3. AMS computer crashed once – successfully restarted
4. SO2 system not connected into HORACE – data logged manually
5. Possible flow problem with filter pack – low flow with some packs
6. SID1 not fitted, SID2 under trial
7. All other instruments performed well

Aircraft

1. Intercom box on Sooty/neph rack is intermittent on TX (reported to Avalon)

Flight extended by 20 minutes to take advantage of good science opportunity downwind of London.

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following logs are not available for flight B111:

Log	Reason
NOxy	No log is ever taken for NOxy
PTrMS	No log is ever taken for PTrMS
CVI	No log is ever taken for CVI
PAN	No log taken or no copy left with FAAM

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

Video recordings from this flight reside with FAAM (at 31 Oct 2005) :

- 2 x Forward Facing Cameras
- 2 x Downward Facing Cameras